

THE PILLAR OF NARI SHAKTI: VIKSIT BHARAT, 2047

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Abstract:

In the view of India nearing to the 100th centenary of Independence 2047, the India is transforming to developed country by the year 2047 under the great vision of Viksit Bharat 2047. It is a strategic intervention to bring a remarkable change in the country and stood the India as a global leader. To achieve the national objective, the government focused on GYAN framework. This constitutes the four pillars of the nation i.e. Garib (Poor), Yuva (Youth), Annadata (Farmer), and Nari (Women). Present the conceptual study focused on the pillar Mahilayen (Women). In the history, the women's are unacknowledged and confined to the family. In recent years there is a notable change in the mindset of women. Women are emerging to social transformation and economic development equal to men. The government also recognized the progress nation depends on the progress of women. To develop the women economically, the schemes such as Pradhan Matri Mudra Yojana, Jandhan Yojna, stand-up India, SHGs and Lakpatti Didi to turn them as Women Entrepreneurs and Women workforce. To reduce the gender selective mortality rate, empowerment through girl child education and provide safety and security the schemes like Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP), Women Helpline, Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA), MUDRA, Mahila Samridhhi Yojana, and many more schemes to protect health and welfare of them. Strengthening the women in all the stages of life is a significant contribution to the society as well as economic development of the nation. In this conceptual paper, presented few schemes supported the women mentally, economically and physically. The outcomes of those schemes are also mentioned.

Key Words: Women Empowerment, Mhailayen, Nari Shakti, Women Workforce, GYAN

Introduction:

The government of India under the leadership of Shri Narendra Modi, Honourable Prime Minister of our country, focused on four major pillars of India i.e. 'Garib' (Poor), 'Mahilayen' (Women), 'Yuva' (Youth) and 'Annadata' (Farmer) and highlighted in the vision of Viksit Bharat, 2047. The main aim of Viksit Bharat is about to develop the capabilities of people and empower them. For the government, the needs, aspirations and welfare of four pillars are the highest priority. The progress of the nation depends on the progress of them. Viksit Bharat 2047 is a persuasive, all-round and inclusive approach for the transformation and development of the nation. To attain this goal, the need for women empowerment is also necessary. So, Nari Shakti (Women Empowerment) is the one of the important caste among the four castes of Viksit Bharat, 2047. The insight of women empowerment is to promote women successfully in all the segments/sectors of India in a healthy, wealthy, safe and satisfactorily. It provides equal opportunities and rights to women in every industry, including Education, Jobs, IT and Politics. The key focus is to increase female workforce participation to 70 per cent. Women, come across challenges in all the stages of life in the form of disparities in society, gender, education and workforce. It leads to a greater contribution to introduce the strategic Interventions for the sustaining of women in all streams of life i.e., individually, socially, psychologically, politically and economically.

Objectives of the Study:

- The primary objective of the study is to know the government schemes that support the pillar Nari Shakti in Vikshit Bharat, 2047
- The secondary objective is to study the outcomes of the government schemes and its contribution to Women and the Nation.

Data:

Present, the study is a conceptual. It highly depends on the secondary data and collected from websites and journals.

Women Education:

Education is a fundamental right of an every citizen. Right to Education is declared as a Human Right at the Universal level. Introduced education to women equal to men with good values and skills from schooling onwards. It helps the women to sustain their life's economically and satisfactorily and boost ups their confidence level individually. They can become economically strong and supports their family. An educated woman led the family ethically, economically, happily and supports the society also.

In India, the school education system consists of 24.69 crore students from pre-school education level to high secondary level. Among, the girl consists of 11.93 crore i.e. 48.3 per cent, which is an incremental improvement. However, the pre-primary enrollment is at 1.4 crores, with a girls strength is at 65.1 lakh i.e. 46.4 per cent compare to boy's strength at 75.3 lakhs i.e. 53.6 per cent.

Unified District Information System for Education Plus (UDISE+) revealed the primary enrollment of students (Class 1-5) stands at 10.44 crore, with girls students at 5.01 crore i.e. 48 per cent. The Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) of girls is 93.3 per cent reflecting the hurdles like safety problems and household chores. The Net Enrollment Ratio (NER) is 76.9 per cent in total and girls is 78.5 per cent.

The dropouts of girl child in Primary education are 0.3% (girls 0.0%), upper primary 3.5% (girls 2.9%), and secondary 11.5% (girls 9.6%). To overcome, The Child Rights and You (CRY) launched the intervention 'Poori Padhai Desh Ki Bhalai' campaign in the year June, 2024. The aim of this campaign is to ensure complete education for girl, under the concept of "Girl Interrupted".

Women Economic Empowerment:

With the support of the government schemes, the women become economically empowered by starting their own enterprises and also women in workforce. The following are the women entrepreneurs who are the inspiration to the women to stand up individually, economically, mentally and physically.

- Falguni Nayar - Founder of **Nykaa** related to Beauty and Wellness products
- Anisha Singh - Co-founder of Mydala related to Local Services Marketing platform
- Richa Kar - Founder of **Zivame** related to Online lingerie
- Shradha Sharma- Founder of **Your Story** related Media Tech platform
- Upasana Taku - Founder of **Mobikwik** related to Digital Wallet and Mobile payment
- Aditi Gupta - Founder of **Menstrypedia** – Social Entrepreneur
- Kiran Mazumdar-Shaw – Founder of **Biocon Enterprises** – Global biopharma
- Ghazal Alagh – Co-founder of **Mamaearth** related to Toxin free Baby Care product
- Malini Agarwal – Founder of **Miss Malini** related to Entertainment

- Malika Shadani – CEO & Founder of **Moms Co.** related to ‘Nature in – Toxic out’ brands
 - Vineet Singh – Founder of **Sugar Cosmetics** related to Cosmetics and Beauty Brands
- Not only as entrepreneurs, majority of the women are in workforce from Top level positions to Lower level in various sectors such as Government Institutions, Corporates and NGO’s. According to the Indian Female Labour Force Participate Ratio (FLFPR) shows the female workforce raised to 41.7 per cent in the year 2023-24 from 23.3 per cent in the year 2017-18. At a moderate level, the women’s are overcoming the challenge of Glass ceiling. At present in India, 30 per cent of GDP of Nation is contributed by the 63 million MSME’s and supported to 110 million of people by providing Jobs.

Women in Politics:

At present, the first citizen of a Nation is the women as ‘President of India’ Honourable President Droupadi Murmur (2022-Incumbent). In the past, ‘Pratiba Patel’ (2007-12) is the first women served as President of India. Late.Indhira Gandhi (1980-84, 1966-72) acted as a Prime Minister of a Nation. At a state level, many women leaders such as Sucheta Kripalani, Shashikala Kalkodkar, J.Jayalalitha are served as Chief Ministers across various states of India. The following are the Indian Women leaders ruled as Chief Ministers of different states.

Table 1: List of Women Leaders as Chief Ministers in Indian History

NAME	STATE	PERIOD
Sucheta Kripalani	Uttar Pradesh	1963 - 67
Nandhini Satpathy	Odisha	1973 - 77
Shashikala Kakodkar	Goa	1973 - 79
Anwara Taimur	Assam	1980 - 81
V.N.Janaki Ramachandran	Tamil Nadu	7th January, 1988 – 30th January,1988
J.Jayalalitha	Tamil Nadu	1991 - 1996
		May 2001 – September, 2001
		2002 – 2006
		2011 – 2014
		2015 – 2016
Mayawati	Uttar Pradesh	1995 – 1995
		March, 1997 – September, 1997
		2002 – 2003
		2007 – 2012
Rajinder Kau Bhattal	Punjab	1996 – 1997
Rabri Devi	Bihar	1997 – 1999
		1999 – 2000
		2000 – 2005
Sushma Swaraj	Delhi	October, 1998 – December, 1998
Sheila Dikshit	Delhi	1998 – 2013
Uma Bharati	Madhya Pradesh	2003 – 2004
Vasundhara Raj	Rajasthan	2003 – 2008
		2013 – 2018
Mamatha Baner Jee	West Bengal	2011 – Incumbent
Anandiben Patel	Gujarat	2014 – 2016
Mehabooba Mufti	Jammu & Khasmir	2016 – 2018
Atishi	Delhi	2024 – 2025
Rekha Gupta	Delhi	2025 - Incumbent

(Source: List of Women Chief Ministers in India)

They are capable of good administrators, reformers and leaders. They are shaping the Indian politics, promoting, leading and inspiring the Indian women and future generations also. Still, women should get an equal opportunity in Parliament, Legislations, Assemblies, Panchayaths and various governing bodies.

Women in Decision Making:

A woman plays an active role in many sectors of society. The women are encouraged to participate in leadership roles for better outcomes at national and international levels.

Government Schemes for Nari Shakti:

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP):

The true meaning of BBBP is ‘*Save the Daughter, Educate the Daughter*’. It was implemented in the year 22nd January, 2015 with Rs.100 crore (US\$13.5 million) funding. The objective of this scheme is to protect the women and empower them through education and safety and to decline child sex ratio or to reduce gender discrimination. It promotes the “Beta Beti, Ek Samaan” (Son and Daughter’s are equal) to overcome the post birth discrimination and sex selective abortion and welfare of the girl child. It is linked to the “Sunkanya Samridhhi Yojana”, only for girl child. Sukanya Samridhhi Yojana (SSY) is a long term saving scheme with high interest rate 9.3 per cent initially and later reduced to 8.2 per cent compare to all the savings account and term deposits, which is meant for girl child education, career and empowerment. The age limit of the girl child is should be below 10 years. The minimum amount is Rs.1000/- per year and the maximum amount is Rs.1,50,000/- year. Up to the 15 years of age of the girl child, the parents have to pay, after that the account will be silent for 6 years. At the age of 21 years, the scheme is matured and the girl will get the eligibility to draw the amount and can be spent for her education, career and marriage etc.On the eve of the 10th Anniversary of the scheme (BBBP), 22nd January, 2025 celebrated. The scheme aligns with Viksit 2047 and shifted from Women’s Development to Women’s Led Development.

Outcomes:

There are more outcomes of this scheme in various dimensions, but very few are presented here:

- The sex ratio of birth is increased to 930 in the year 2023-24 compare to previous years i.e. 918(2014-15), 934 (2019-20).
- In Education the GER is increased from 75.51 per cent (2024-15) to 78 per cent in the year 2023-24.
- There is a drastic increase in the Health from 61 per cent (2014-15) to 97.3 per cent (2023-24)

National Commission for Women (NCW) Women Helpline:

It is introduced in the year 21st July, 2021 and operated by the National Commission for Women (NCW), New Delhi. It is the NCW 24*7 Women Helpline toll-free emergency number 14490. The aim is to a provide Digital Complaint Registration System against the violence affected by the women. It provides services like assistance, support from various challenges faced by the women, legal assistance, counseling and guidance on issues like sexual harassment, domestic violence and distress. It also connects to the police, one stop centres, hospitals and the other authorities who protect them.Added to this number,

some other toll-free helpline numbers such as Emergency Response Support System (ERSS) is 112, Women Helpline (WHL) is 181, Childline is 1098 and 1930 is the Cyber crime helpline number, which works actively to ensure the women protection and children safety. It was initiated and funded by the Government of India under the Nirbhaya fund. It is operated under the Ministry of Women and Child Development. The toll-free women helpline number 181 is introduced under NITI-Aayog in the year 2020-21.

Outcomes:

Vimalkumar Makwana and Chancel Jayaram (2022) studied on Impact of 181 Helpline Implementation with reference to Status of Women in the village of Vadodara. The study revealed that majority of the women i.e. 56.6 per cent contacted the 181 helpline to give complaint on Harassment on Social Sites (48 per cent), Harassment on Phone (44 per cent) and Domestic violence (8 per cent). They came to know about this helpline from Social Media with highest of 61.9 per cent, with moderate is friends/family (34.9 per cent) and the rest is through advertisements (3.2 per cent).

Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA):

On 31st July, 2016, PMSMA is launched to provide quality antenatal care to all pregnant women’s universally in the 2nd, 3rd trimester and in 9th of every month. It is applicable to rural and urban women’s. It helps in identifying and follows up the high risk pregnancies and red stickers are placed to the high risk pregnancies and infants. For the low risk pregnancies, a green sticker attached. The government also involved the private physicians under this scheme and to be a part of this program. To be among this program, registration is compulsory to the physicians. The PMSMA aligns with broader goals of the Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health plus Nutrition (RMNCAH+N) strategy under the **National Health Mission (NHM)**.

Outcomes:

- As of December 31st 2024, the high risk pregnancies have been identified across all states/UTs, which is more than 78.27 lakhs.
- With the government efforts ensures the antenatal care and nutritional care for pregnant women shows significant impact on India’s Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR), declined from 130 per lakh live birth in 2014-16 to 80 lakhs live birth in 2021-23.

(Graph1)

(Graph 2)

(Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressNoteDetails.aspx?id=154588&NoteId=154588&ModuleId=3®=3&lang=2>)

The above Graph 1 shows the state wise the number physicians voluntarily registered to be a part of this program. The highest number of physicians volunteer registered state is the Maharashtra with 1131 follows on Uttar Pradesh with 1076, Rajasthan with 1015, Madhya Pradesh with 615 and the rest Karnataka with 615. The above Graph 2 shows the Top five states received by Antenatal care under PMSMA of May 2025. Majority of the people 1,89,534 from the Uttar Pradesh received the PMSMA followed by Madhya Pradesh with 38,573, Andhra Pradesh with 36216, Gujarat with 24,039 and the rest West Bengal with 23,102.

Table 2: Registered Physicians Voluntarily and the facilities of PMSMA

Component	Actual Numbers (at present)
Volunteer Registered	6,813
Number of Facilities providing PMSMA services	20,752

The above Table 2 shows the systematic involvement of the private practitioners voluntarily in this program for the campaigns and awareness on the same. The volunteer Registered number is 6, 813 members and the number of facilities provided under PMSMA are 20,752.

The following Graph 3 shows the Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) in India. With the efforts of Government in providing the antenatal care for pregnant women showed a notable development in India’s MMR. There is a declined from 130 per lakh live birth in 2014-16 to 80 per lakh live birth in 2021-23, which is a reduction of 50 points.

Graph 3: Maternal Mortality Ratio

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY):

It is implemented in the year 8th April, 2015 by Prime Minister of India Shri Narendra Modi. It is a Central Government Scheme, provides the loans up to Rs.10 Lakhs to the Non-form small/Micro Enterprises, Non-Corporate and other income generated activities. It stands for the true spirit of 'Sabka Saath Sabka Vikas'. The meaning of MUDRA means Money Capital.

The expansion of MUDRA is Micro Units Development & Refinance Agency. It is collateral free loans. The loans were given by the Commercial Banks, RRB's (Regional Rural Banks), SFB's (State Financial Banks), MFI (Micro Financial Institutions) and National Banking Financial Companies (NBFC). The loans are given in the following categories:

- Shishu (Start-ups) – Loans up to Rs 50,000
- Kishore (Existed & Small) – Loans from Rs 50,000 upto Rs 5,00,000
- Tarun (Well Established) – Loans from Rs 5,00,000 upto Rs 10,00,000
- Traun Plus – Loans from Rs.10,00,000 upto Rs.20,00,00

Outcomes:

- To till March, 2022, more than 34.42 crore loan accounts amounted to Rs.18.60 lakh crore extended under PMMY
- Out of this, Rs.8.10 lakhs crore i.e. more than 23.27 crore loans extended to women borrowers. It shows 68 per cent of loan (35.38 crore loans worth Rs.14.72 lakhs crore) constitutes for women and 44 per cent of the beneficiaries are under the scheme of **PM SVANidhi to support street vendors**. It drives to rise in women self-employment across India.
- In the between the financial year 2016 to 2025, the average disbursement amount of women borrower is increased at a CAGR of 13 per cent Rs.62,679
- To the April, 2025, Women received over Rs.14.72 lakhs crore in loans to set up and expand Micro Enterprises.
- The States with high women-led MSME employment, such as Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, and Karnataka are the major beneficiaries.

Other Schemes such as:

Namo Drone Didi Scheme:

The Government of India introduced 'Namo Drone Didi' for providing 15000 drones to Women SHG's with an amount of Rs.1261 Crores for the year 2023-24 to 2025-26. The objective of the scheme is to promote advance technology in agriculture to improve the productivity, to reduce cost of operation, to empower SHG's Drone service providers for increasing their income and provide livelihood. This scheme provides 80 per cent financial assistance for the package and 15 days training. So far, for the financial year 2023-24, 1094 drones were distributed and 1094 were trained across the states and 14,500 were allocated state wise.

Mahila Samridhi Yojana:

It is Central Government Scheme, provides Micro Loans upto Rs.1.40 Lakhs to Sanitation Workers and Poor Women for self-employment. The National Safai Karamchari's Finance & Development Corporation (NSFDC) provides funding at concession interest rates to start their own business such as Handicrafts, Small Industries, Agriculture and Tailoring etc.

DAY-NRLM:

The expansion of DAY NRLM is **Deendayal Antodaya Yojana National Rural Livelihood Mission**. It is started in the year 2011, to provide livelihood to below poverty line under the Ministry of Rural Development. It aims to empower the rural poor, particularly women. It organizes women into Self Help Groups. Now, DAY-NRLM is known for financial inclusion, sustainable livelihood and skill development to households to get out of their poverty.

Criminalised the Triple-Talaq:

Protection of Rights on Marriage Act, 2019 enacted in the year 2019 to protect the Muslim Women and her dependent children from Triple-Talaq in India i.e. Criminalized Talaq-e-biddat. It is an offense and non-bailable. The offended husband faced up to 3years prison and fine also

Conclusion:

Through Nari Shakti, Women empower by Education, Entrepreneurship, Women Workforce participation and Skill Development. Viksit Bharat, 2047 is a moral and strategic vision to empower the women and reduce the gender gaps. It provides the guarantee opportunities, economic development, and education and enforces the law for gender equality.

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